

Didactic Games Used in Natural Science Classes
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Abstract: *This article talks about various interesting didactic games for elementary school students to use in natural science lessons. These didactic games help students to learn the knowledge of natural sciences in the best possible way. These types of games allow you to revise information about various fields of natural sciences and countries of the world. The games provide a broad understanding of the world space in the future, and attract the views of this field of knowledge and improve the way of thinking of students. develops further."Applause" game, "Five fingers" game, "Around the world in 8 minutes" game, "Quick find" game and others.*

Keywords: didactic game, student, natural sciences, to impart knowledge, to teach, to form.

I.INTRODUCTION

As it is known, various conditions are being created for the elementary classes, which are the basis of education for the future of our country and the education of the young generation, and solutions to educational problems are being provided.[1] Also, from the 2021-2022 academic year, the 1st-2nd grade textbooks of natural sciences were introduced to schools. Now, in all general education schools, a textbook of natural sciences is taught, which combines the basic concepts of several subjects: the world around us, natural science, geography, biology and physics. Science, intended for grades 1-4 of general secondary education, combines several subjects and provides integration with many social and economic subjects based on the STEAM system.[5]

II.MATERIALS AND METHODS

This tutorial has the following priorities:

- Teaching topics from simple to complex;
- Based on the topics, life topics that occur in everyday life, experiences, and small projects are included in accordance with the age of the students.
- In order to develop students' logical thinking abilities in natural science textbooks, first questions are asked, then the topic is explained, the topics are often presented in the form of pictures and illustrations.
- Now, in this textbook, QR codes are provided for each subject in accordance with the 21st century, and if the smartphone is held to the QR code on the textbook cover, children can see the object they are studying moving, hear its sound, or learn about other features of that object. will be possible.[5]

The main features of didactic games in natural science classes are as follows:

- when games are used during the lesson, students develop developmental activities;

- creating a creative environment and discussions during the games. In the process of performing tasks, they solve their problems in cooperation with the group.[4]

The teacher prepares for the games in advance. Whatever method or didactic games are used, the goal of the lesson will be achieved and the efficiency will be high. For this, the pedagogue develops the structure of the game:

- creating the goal and project of the game;
- to determine the participants of the game;
- development of tasks of the participants;
- determining the relationship between the participants.[4]

III. RESULTES AND DISCUSSION

1. **"Around the world in 8 minutes" game.** The goal of the game: to form students' skills of resourcefulness, harmony, and responsiveness. The name of this game itself attracts students to the game. The conditions of the game are as follows: the teacher says the name of the country, then the student finds this country on the map, instead of the name of the country, the image of this country is written on the map. Then the student should say the capital of this country. If he finds the capital city correctly, he answers the question on the studied topics and gets 5 points. If this game is played in 2 groups of 5 students, the result will be high and students will learn to work together in a group.

2. **"Applause" game.** The purpose of the game: to check students' knowledge, to activate students. In the game, the teacher says the terms and words related to natural sciences. If the word refers to this subject, the students clap, if not, they do not clap. A student who makes a mistake will leave the game. If this game is used during a break, when students are bored and activity drops, the effectiveness of the lesson will increase. For example, words to use: mountain, computer, planet, earth, sky, wardrobe, map, plant, gardener, boot, ...

3. **"Five fingers" game.** The purpose of the game: to control the knowledge of the students on the topics covered, to achieve the effectiveness of the lesson. In the game, the shape of the hand is made and cut. A question is written on each finger. If the student answers the question incorrectly, he bends his finger. After 5 questions, the number of unbent fingers on the student's hand represents the student's grade.

IV. CONCLUSION

These innovations are very convenient for elementary school students and make it easier to learn knowledge. The use of didactic games and methods in natural science classes makes the lessons interesting, the students do not get bored, the students are quick, clever, resourceful, observant, able to check things, find their differences, and strengthen their memory. helps the teacher.

Also, the use of the following didactic games in elementary science classes helps to achieve the lesson goal and increase efficiency.

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